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TORBEAM 2.0 on TCV

Internship

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Preface

I would like to thank my daily supervisors Federico and Olivier for their, knowledge, guidance and support. In the first few weeks, for example, I had the opportunity to devise a comparison plan between TORAY and TORBEAM, execute it, and share results. Directly comparing to results in [18] left many discrepancies open for interpretation. Fruitful suggestions presented an alternative path with a smaller step size. This occurred to me while teaching. As I ask a student to point at -3.3 on the numberline. Pointing at -2.7, he misses the step of starting to search between -3 and -4. These steps, how simple they may seem, have to occur to a person. As such I believe Federico and Olivier have shown me to keep looking for intermediate steps and leave little key results open for interpretation.

Simultaneously I am obliged to dedicate a section to Covid-19 in my report, that is this section. Thank you Federico for helping with GitLab, inviting me to bi-weekly discussions on ZOOM and to be part of the community (you could have rejected my remote internship). The presentations, discussions, and foremost people at the Swiss Plasma Center as part of the École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL) have been instructive and inspiring. Thank you Olivier for showing GUIprofs and your efforts of teaching French. Thank you Cristian for your support during one of the Covid infections in my dorm ("hard times") and your help with C++ and Simulink. Thank you, Federico, Olivier, and Cristian for responding on Slack, mostly within 15 minutes, I have had different experiences under different circumstances.

Thank you Egbert for sharing your knowledge and suggestions. For your efforts on clarifying and discussing the absorption of a beam in a plasma with a drawing (recreated in Figure 2.4) and for arranging a working place at DIFFER (even though it did not last long). Also for the chocolate and cooking gear that made me feel part of the community at DIFFER, even if just a little.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Electron cyclotron heating (ECH) and electron cyclotron current drive (ECCD) can be used for plasma startup and various control purposes, including control of the current density distribution and mitigation or suppression of Magneto Hydro Dynamic (MHD) instabilities. In these cases, the EC wave is coupled to the plasma and deposits energy and/or drives current at tactical locations. The location of wave deposition can be determined by beam-tracing codes that utilize the plasma equilibrium and launcher angles in a specified geometry. The beam-tracing code TORBEAM has recently been extended with real-time (RT) capabilities that include the calculation of the current drive (E. Poli 2018).

The current drive is required in the real-time simulation of the current density with the RAPTOR code that solves the parallel current diffusion equation [5]. This requires all current drive sources to be known and is already used for a wealth of applications where real-time knowledge is used for feedback control and disruption avoidance in a tokamak. Specifically on disruption avoidance, the current drive determines a term in the Modified Rutherford Equation (MRE). The MRE can be used to calculate the time-evolution of magnetic islands caused by neoclassical tearing modes, an MHD instability. These instabilities (magnetic islands) can lock to the reactor wall (Lenz's Law) and cause a disruption of the plasma. In future fusion experiments and high performance fusion reactors the boundaries of stable operation are pushed by design. In these regimes of operations, small disturbances seed instabilities and can lead to disruptions if not accounted for. The occurrence of disruptions in a fusion power plant is undesirable. As shown by [8], the MRE can be used in predictive real-time control schemes to suppress instabilities and mitigate disruptions while using the RAPTOR code.

The inclusion in the real-time current density simulation code (RAPTOR) [5] that complements the additional information of the current drive in as used by [8] is the main motivator for the implementation of real-time TORBEAM on TCV. This report discusses the implementation of TORBEAM (TBM) and real-time TORBEAM (RT-TBM) on the Tokamak à Configuration Variable (TCV). The report is structured as follows. Firstly, some background is provided for readers with little knowledge on nuclear fusion, Electron Cyclotron Heating (ECH), and Electron Cyclotron Current Drive (ECCD). Secondly, the new implementation of TORBEAM is compared to the installed and verified ray-tracing code TORAY-GA. Thirdly, validated real-time TORBEAM is used to determine the launching angles required to reach a location of wave deposition, to reverse ray-trace (the second motivator).

Chapter 2

Background

The Swiss Plasma Centre (SPC) operates the Tokamak à Configuration Variable (TCV) in Lausanne, Switzerland. TCV is an experimental reactor that aids the development of nuclear fusion and thus contributes to zero-carbon reliable energy source without long lived nuclear waste and a fuel supply that outlives the Sun. The inside of the machine is visible in Figure 2.1. The machine has the shape of a vertically elongated Torus with major radius $R = 0.88$ meter and minor radius of $a = 0.25$ meter. The magnetic field can reach a maximum of 1.54 Tesla and can achieve a variety of plasma shapes. Plasma is formed by inducing a loop voltage in the torus. Free electrons collide with atoms that release more electrons and cause an avalanche of free electrons. This process is called breakdown and a plasma is born in the form of a cloud with charged particles. The charged particles experience a Lorentz force as they move in strong magnetic fields and they start gyrating around the magnetic field lines. The magnetic field is configured such that the field lines go around in the torus in Figure 2.1. As the particles follow the magnetic field they also go around in the torus and trace their own tails. In the ideal case, the particles go in circles forever, in this case the particles are magnetically confined. This magnetic confinement can be used to reach the conditions required for fusion reactions. TCV can reach particle densities of $1\text{-}20 \cdot 10^{19}$ [$1/\text{m}^3$] and temperatures of up to 15 kilo electronvolts (over 100 million degrees). These extreme temperatures can be reached by externally heating the plasma. At TCV, energetic particles are injected with a power of up to 1 Megawatt by one Neutral Beam Injector (NBI) and Electron Cyclotron (EC) waves can be coupled to the plasma with a power of up to 2.3 Megawatt using gyrotrons. Next to this very high power density Electron Cyclotron Heating (ECH), TCV is characterized by extreme flexibility in plasma shaping and positioning.

Figure 2.1: The inside of TCV.

Magnetic Topology

Previously it was stated that the charged particles follow the magnetic field and go around the torus forever. The problem is that the particles tend to drift from the magnetic field lines. They drift up and down because the magnetic field is stronger near the center wall (High Field Side, HFS) than near the outer wall (Low Field Side, LFS). This is the gradient B ($\nabla \vec{B}$) drift for which the electrons and ions drift in opposite directions and setup a vertical electric field. The electric field produces a Lorentz force that causes the ions and electrons to drift outward, the ($\vec{E} \times \vec{B}$) drift. The last drift considered here is caused by the curvature of the magnetic field (bending of lines). Fortunately, the drifts on the HFS and LFS have opposite signs due to the axi-symmetry of the torus and sum to zero by means of a rotational transform. This rotational transform can be created with a toroidal (going around the torus) plasma current, induced via a changing vertical magnetic flux. The plasma current creates a poloidal magnetic field (in the plane of a circular slice of the torus) that interacts with the particles and makes them move diagonally over toroidal surfaces.

The toroidal surfaces are visible in Figure 2.2 (taken from [1]) where, in red, the toroidal magnetic field \vec{B}_ϕ is created by magnetic coils and the poloidal magnetic field \vec{B}_θ is formed by the plasma current along the magnetic axis. Together the poloidal and toroidal fields form helical magnetic fields \vec{B} (the green line) that are traced by plasma particles. In this configuration, the resulting magnetic fields form nested toroidal flux surfaces. Transport over these surfaces is magnitudes higher than transport between these surfaces, as such the temperature and density are almost constant on a toroidal surface. The nested toroidal surfaces are labeled by the normalized radial coordinate ρ , which is 0 at the magnetic axis and 1 at the plasma boundary (ρ_b).

Figure 2.2: Toroidal magnetic flux surfaces in a tokamak plasma. The limiting flux surface at the plasma core is called the magnetic axis and (R, Z) define the radial and vertical coordinates in the poloidal plane [1]

Electron Cyclotron Heating

With the particles well confined in the magnetic topology of the reactor, it is possible to heat the plasma and reach reasonable densities with high temperatures. At high temperatures, one of the main heating mechanisms is Radio Frequency (RF) heating. RF heating utilizes the interaction between electromagnetic waves and charged particles in a wave-particle resonance. Electrons, for instance, gyrate around magnetic field lines with the electron cyclotron frequency ($\omega_{ce} = eB/m_e$) and resonate with the injected wave. This form of RF heating is called Electron Cyclotron Heating.

At TCV, a Gyrotron generates these waves in bundles (beams) at a frequency of 82.7 GHz. The waves are guided from the gyrotron to the launchers. In Figure 2.3 (a) the schematic depicts an X-2 launcher that can rotate around ϕ_L between shots and contains mirror that is steerable in real-time over θ_L . In Figure 2.3 (b) upper (#2, #5, #6) and equatorial (#1, #4) launchers are schematically represented by four mirrors and a wave source. The upper launcher injects waves downwards in the poloidal cross-section of the plasma ($\phi_L = 0$). The equatorial launchers injects upwards because it is rotated $\phi_L = 180^\circ$. The injected rays are absorbed at the magnetic resonance (dashed line) and these locations are denoted by red dots. The dots are on top of elongated magnetic flux surfaces which are labeled by the normalized radius (ρ). The normalized radius equals zero on the magnetic axis ($\rho = 0$) and one on the last closed flux surface ($\rho = 1$), the plasma edge. On the left in (b) the launch angles and their corresponding deposition location form a mapping ($\theta \approx 90^\circ - \theta_L \leftrightarrow \rho$). In this map, forward raytracing (red) of a launch angle presents a unique deposition location, while the inverse request (blue) of the launch angle to reach a target location (ρ_{tar}) can yield two solutions ($\theta_{tar}^{(*)}$).

The

Figure 2.3: Schematic of the X-2 launchers (a)[3] with mirror steerable in θ_L in real-time. The launcher can be rotated as one body in θ_L between shots [3]. In (b), the launchers are schematically represented by four mirrors and a ray-source. An upper launcher injects waves in the poloidal cross-section ($\phi_L = 0^\circ$). These waves are absorbed at the magnetic resonant surface (X-2 1.5T) and denoted by red points. The red points are on top of magnetic flux surfaces labeled by ρ and mapped to the launch angle in the graph to the left. In the map, forward raytracing of θ_L (red) presents ρ_{dep} (red) while inverse raytracing of ρ_{target} (blue) yields two solutions $\theta_{tar}^{(*)}$ (blue)

Wave Propagation and Absorption in a Plasma

In order to model the propagation of electromagnetic waves in a plasma, the particles are assumed to be immersed in a vacuum. The influence of plasma behavior is described by the dielectric tensor [6]. The dielectric tensor results from Fourier analysis and linearization on Maxwell's equations. The dielectric tensor is characterized as $\overleftrightarrow{\mathbf{K}}$ and describes the effects of the plasma on wave propagation:

$$\overleftrightarrow{\mathbf{K}} = \overleftrightarrow{\mathbf{I}} + \frac{i}{\epsilon_0 \omega} \overleftrightarrow{\sigma}, \quad (2.1)$$

as such it depends on a plasma model that determines the conductivity tensor ($\overleftrightarrow{\sigma}$), the vacuum permittivity ϵ_0 and the imaginary i . The dielectric tensor determines the relation between wave frequency (ω) and wave vector (\mathbf{k}), a dispersion function written as $D(\omega, \mathbf{k})$ [6]. Both weakly and fully relativistic dielectric tensors can describe fully and/or weakly relativistic emission, dispersion, and absorption of plasma waves [6].

In fusion physics, the most important wave-types are characterized by the polarization (alignment of wave vector k with the wave field E) and denoted by O and X mode (O mode has $E_{\parallel} \neq 0$, X mode has $E_{\parallel} = 0$). The energy from these wave-types is absorbed by the plasma via a wave-particle resonance. A wave-particle resonance requires the following condition to hold:

$$\omega = k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel} + l \omega_c \quad l = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (2.2)$$

Which means that resonance occurs when the parallel Doppler shifted frequency of the wave ($\omega - k_{\parallel} v_{\parallel}$) is equal to an exact (l^{th}) harmonic of the cyclotron frequency ($\omega_c = (eB)/m_e$). The resonance between a ray (\vec{s}_{θ}) and the magnetic surface (B) is schematically depicted as an oscillation in Figure 2.4.a. In (b), two rays are shown in the toroidal (\vec{s}_{ϕ}) and poloidal (\vec{s}_{θ}) plane. In the poloidal plane this corresponds to on- and off-axis and in the toroidal plane to oblique and perpendicular injection, with respect to the flux surface ψ .

The electron velocity is represented by a distribution around the electron temperature (T_e) in which the velocity parallel to the magnetic field is much larger than its perpendicular counterpart ($v_{\parallel} \gg v_{\perp}$). For oblique injection the distributed parallel electron velocities (v_{\parallel}) result in a series of magnetic surfaces that satisfy Eq. 2.2. Unlike perpendicular injection, where $v_{\parallel} = 0$. Hence, the red absorption region is far more stretched than the blue one. In (c), the ray \vec{s} is part of a beam with diameter (\vec{w}) which is absorbed in the blue or red boxes that are projected to the poloidal plane in (d). In (e) the absorbed power is projected on the plasma radius and denoted with units MW/m^3 because 3D absorption is mapped ρ (1D).

Figure 2.4: The ray/beam injected in (a) maps to the poloidal/toroidal plane as ray in (b) and as beam in (c). Equation 2.2 determines the colored regions in (b,c,d), which are mapped to the plasma radius in (e).

Chapter 3

Forward Ray Tracing

The TCV ECH system is designed to assist in reaching various advanced operating regimes, for real-time control of the plasma profiles, and for suppression of instabilities. The goal of forward raytracing is to know the deposition of power and current, given the launcher settings and information about the plasma. In TCV, the raytracing code TORAY-GA determines the power and current deposition of the EC beams after the shot, while the real-time version of TORBEAM is used to determine the real-time deposition of the beams. The following sections discuss the implementation of TORAY-GA at TCV and the new version of TORBEAM [16] in detail.

3.1 TORAY

The following section elaborates on the TORAY code used to check the implemented TORBEAM 2.0 code. Where TORBEAM uses a Gaussian propagation model, TORAY propagates multiple rays from the launcher to determine the propagation of the beam. The rays are spatially arranged such that the averaged power density along the ensemble approximates that of a Gaussian beam [9]. Absorption is calculated independently on each ray, which can cause non Gaussian radial power profiles in the beam. This can be an important effect when the beam approaches the resonance at a steep angle. Typically 30-100 rays are adequate to simulate a beam [9].

Ray Launching

In TORAY-GA, the ray pattern of an antenna can be simulated by a set of rays with a given shape, a ray pattern. At TCV a custom ray pattern generator is used to produce rays that approximate a Gaussian distribution on the last mirror. The width of the distribution corresponds to the waist of the beam and emulates the beam spot on the last mirror. The ray pattern is projected on the last closed flux surface which can be seen in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: The ray pattern and beam waist of TORAY, at the LCFS.

Ray Tracing

According to the manual [7], TORAY follows the trajectory or rays in the electron cyclotron frequency range $\omega \approx \Omega_e$ as they propagate through the plasma. The frequency and wave number are related by the dispersion relation

$$D(\mathbf{k}, \omega, \mathbf{x}) = 0, \quad (3.1)$$

assuming that the background plasma is in steady state. The wave trajectory is found by solving the raytracing equations:

$$\frac{d\vec{r}}{ds} = -\frac{\partial D / \partial \vec{k}}{|\partial D / \partial \vec{k}|}, \quad (3.2)$$

$$\frac{d\vec{k}}{ds} = \frac{\partial D / \partial \vec{r}}{|\partial D / \partial \vec{k}|}, \quad (3.3)$$

where s is the arclength along the ray path, \vec{k} is the wavenumber, \vec{r} is the spatial position, and D is determined from the dispersion relation by a cold or warm plasma approximation. The wave front moves with the group velocity as

$$\mathbf{v}_g = \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial \mathbf{k}} = \frac{\partial D / \partial \mathbf{k}}{\partial D / \partial \omega}. \quad (3.4)$$

The fraction of RF power absorbed by the plasma is given by the integral along the ray path:

$$p(s) = 1 - \exp\left(-2 \int_0^s \text{Im}(\vec{k}) \cdot \frac{d\vec{r}}{ds}\right), \quad (3.5)$$

where the imaginary part of \vec{k} is obtained from the solution of the dispersion relation. The power decrement over some arc length ds is $\text{Im}(\vec{k})$ evaluated at the end of the step multiplied by ds . The power in a ray over its trajectory is calculated using

$$dP = 2k_i ds \cos(\phi) P, \quad (3.6)$$

where dP is the decrement in the power P of a ray in taking a step of size ds along its trajectory, k_i is the imaginary part of the wavevector, and ϕ is the angle between the wave vector and the magnetic field.

TCV Settings

At TCV, the solution of the dispersion relation is calculated with the Matsuda-Hu model on wave absorption near the 2nd and 3th harmonic (depending on the launcher) and made for weakly relativistic regimes. The ECCD module of LinLiu is used at TCV, which corresponds to the default option at DIII-D. The settings as used for TORAY-GA at TCV are presented in Tables 3.1 and 3.2. The ray pattern is generated by a custom circular Gaussian ray distribution function ('.file') which is very likely using a radius of curvature of 53.2 [cm] and a waist radius of 2.3 [cm] to emulate the beam spot at the last mirror. This beam spot is propagated to the last closed flux surface, where TORAY starts raytracing. A ray pattern at the last flux surface can be seen in Figure 3.2, along with a $1/e^2$ waist for TORAY and TORBEAM. These are extracted from the later comparisons in figures C.2 and 3.5 using the angle conventions from Appendix A.

Table 3.1: Input settings for TORAY-GA at TCV from 'inone.toray'.

Setting	Description	Value
igafit	Switch to call GAFIT EFIT interface	0
smax	maximum arclength of ray [cm]	400
ds	initial step size of arclength [cm]	0.2
dsmn	adjustable step size of arclength [cm]	0.02
fdout	ray output every fdout step	1.0
relerr	relative error tolerance in y-solution vector of ODE solver	5E-05
abserr	absolute error tolerance in ODE solver	5E-05
ezeff	Z_{rmeff}	2.0
nharm	harmonic number	2-3
mn0	number of mesh pts in Gaussian integration	32
bsratio	specifies antenna shape (1=circ, $\neq 1$ =elongated)	1
raypatt	ray pattern model ('.km.' = old Matsude model)	'file.'
gauszone	number of annuli for Gaussian ray pattern model	3
modelc	module for ECCD calculation (3= Cohen,4 = LinLiu)	4

Table 3.2: TORAY-GA 'echin' quantities at TCV with description and values.

Setting	Description	Value
idamp	Damping model	2-3
j12	number of profile points	101
nbfld	equilibrium type (1=concentric circles, 3 = EFIT)	3
psinrmr(j12)	normalized toroidal flux, $\rho/\rho(a)$	-
Zef(j12)	effective charge, Z_{eff}	2
ene(j12)	electron density [cm^{-3}]	-
ete(j12)	electron temperature [keV]	-

3.2 TORBEAM 2.0

The TORBEAM code uses a beam tracing formalism with a cold plasma dispersion relation to determine the trajectory for the beam center [17]. The code has been updated recently [16], this includes a real-time version that calculates the point of maximum absorption, the total driven current and a single-ray estimate of the deposition width. The Gaussian beam formalism was developed for scenarios where interference or diffraction is important [9].

Ray Tracing

The code uses the paraxial Wentzel-Kramers-Brillouin (WKB) method for the propagation of high-frequency waves in inhomogeneous anisotropic media[16]. The solution of the vector wave equation

$$\frac{c^2}{\omega^2} \nabla \times (\nabla \times \mathbf{E}) - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \cdot \mathbf{E} = 0 \quad (3.7)$$

is found in the high-frequency limit

$$\kappa \equiv \frac{\omega L}{c} = k_0 L \gg 1, \quad (3.8)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ is the dielectric tensor, $\omega/2\pi$ is the wave frequency, c is the speed of light, L the inhomogeneity of the medium and k_0 the vacuum vector. For a Gaussian beam, the complex-eikonal *ansatz* for the electric field results in a simplified solution

$$\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}) = A(\mathbf{r})\mathbf{e}(\mathbf{r})e^{ik_0[s(\mathbf{r})+i\phi(\mathbf{r})]}, \quad (3.9)$$

where ϕ describes field amplitude across the beam cross-section. The complex-eikonal electric field results in a beam width W that satisfies

$$\frac{\lambda}{W} \approx \frac{W}{L} \approx \frac{1}{\sqrt{\kappa}}, \quad (3.10)$$

where λ is the vacuum wavelength. The complex-eikonal electric field is Taylor expanded around the reference ray (paraxial expansion):

$$\begin{aligned} s(\mathbf{r}) &= s_0(\mathbf{r}) + \mathcal{N}_\alpha [x_\alpha - q_\alpha] + \frac{1}{2} s_{\alpha\beta} [x_\alpha - q_\alpha] [x_\beta - q_\beta], \\ \phi(\mathbf{r}) &= \frac{1}{2} \phi_{\alpha\beta} [x_\alpha - q_\alpha] [x_\beta - q_\beta], \end{aligned} \quad (3.11)$$

where q_α and \mathbf{N}_α are the components of the position vector $\{x_\alpha\} \equiv \mathbf{r}$ and of the refractive index $\{N_\alpha\} \equiv \nabla s$, on the reference ray. The second order coefficients $\phi_{\alpha\beta}$ are related to the curvature while the coefficients $s_{\alpha\beta}$ are connected to the width of the amplitude profile [17]. The quantities $q_\alpha, \mathcal{N}_\alpha, S_{\alpha\beta}$ and $\phi_{\alpha\beta}$ result from the beam tracing equations described in 19 ordinary differential equations (ODEs), where the beam power only needs to be evaluated on the reference ray.

Real-Time Version

The real-time version of TORBEAM only considers the reference ray, which reduces the number of ODEs to 7. The deposition profiles are not calculated and the grid size on which the equilibrium and kinetic profiles are defined is limited to 150 points. A further reduction in computation time is achieved through extrapolated plasma coefficients during the integration of the 7 ODEs [16]. At TCV this routine achieves computation times of approximately 5 ms.

TCV Settings

At TCV, the real-time TORBEAM raytracing code is implemented in Matlab Simulink via a *mex* file integrated in a Simulink *S – function*. TORBEAM and thus the wrapper require a settings of type double and type integer. The integer type input settings are presented in Table 3.3 and the input settings of type double are presented in Table 3.4.

The integer settings in Table 3.3 are set for interpolated density and temperature profiles and an experimental equilibrium, since these will be run on TCV.

- **nmod**: the considered launchers use X-mode waves that are absorbed at the second harmonic.
- **nrela**: similarly to the TORAY-GA settings in Table 3.2 the absorption model is weakly relativistic, meaning a weakly relativistic dielectric tensor is used to formulate a dispersion relation.
- **nprofcalc**: the standard deposition profile is not able to produce on-axis heating and current drive, but the à la Maj routine setting that integrates the continuity equation for the wave energy density was not available at the time of writing.
- **ncdharm**: the additional harmonic in the current drive efficiency is important for cases in which the lowest harmonic does not dominate absorption as it becomes accessible [16] (shown for ITER half-field scenario).
- **nptns**, **nfreq**: the plasma coefficients can be coarsely extrapolated and interpolated during the integrations of a ray to reduce computation time. However, **npnts** and **nfreq** are set to 1 because these values are also used by TORBEAM (which does not extrapolate). Moreover, at this stage accuracy, outweighs the small reduction in execution time reported by [16].
- **ncdroutine**: the current drive routine is set to LinLiu because this is similar to the setting of TORAY or to Lin-Liu+mom because this is physically more correct and the default at ASDEX Upgrade (AUG) [16]. LinLiu+Mom is set as default at AUG since it is numerically efficient and accurate.
- **nastra**: the Lin-Liu definition is used to compare the current drive density, it is assumed that Lin-Liu will give the correct definition since the current drive routine was originally developed by Lin-Liu and both TORAY and TOBEAM use a current drive routine named by Lin-Liu.

Table 3.3: Settings for *intinbeam* with description and the inputs used.

Setting	Description	Value
nmod (*)	O-mode (1), X-mode (-1)	(-1)
npow (*)	power absorption on(1)/off(0)	(1)
ncd (*)	current drive calculation on(1)/off(0)	(1)
ianexp (*)	analytic (1) or experimental (2) equilibrium	(2)
ncdroutine	Curba (0), Lin-Liu (1), Lin-Liu+mom.cons (2)	(?)
nprofv	number of points for volume profile	(20)
nrela	weakly (0) or fully (1) relativistic absorption	(0)
nmaxh	number of harmonics $1 \leq nmaxh \leq 5$	(2)
nabsroutine	Westerhof (0) or Farina (1)	(1)
nastra	Def. of j_{CD} : Lin-Liu (0), ASTRA(1), JINTRAC(2)	(?)
nprofcalc	Standard dep. profiles (0), profiles à la Maj (1)	(0)
ncdharm	Only lowest (0) or also next (1) harmonic in CD efficiency	(1)
npnts_extrap (rt. only)	number of points used in coef. extrapolation (default 3)	(1)
nfreq_extrap (rt. only)	number of steps on which coef. are extrapolated (default 6)	(1)

Table 3.4: Settings for *floatinbeam* with description and used input values.

Setting	Description	Value
xf (*)	wave frequency in Hz ($\omega = 2\pi \cdot \text{xf}$)	$82.7 \cdot 10^9$
xordeg (*)	toroidal injection angle [deg]	-15.3
xpoldeg (*)	poloidal injection angle [deg]	37.8
xxb (*)	x-coordinate of launch point [cm]	114
xyb (*)	y-coordinate of launch point [cm]	0
xzb (*)	z-coordinate of launch point [cm]	44
xrtol (*)	required rel. error	$3 \cdot 10^{-7}$
xatol (*)	required abs. error	$3 \cdot 10^{-7}$
xstep (*)	integration step in vacuum [cm]	0.2
xryyb (not rt)	initial principal curvature radius [cm]	53.2
xrzzb (not rt)	initial principal curvature radius [cm]	53.2
xwyyb (not rt)	initial principal width [cm]	2.3
xwzzb (not rt)	initial principal width [cm]	2.3
xpw0 (*)	initial beam power [MW]	0.4239
xrmaj (*)	geometrical major radius [cm]	88
xrmin (*)	minor radius [cm] (for normalization)	25
sgnm ()	flux has a max. ($\text{sgnm}=-1$) or a min. ($\text{sgnm}=1$) on magn. axis	-1
xzeff	effective charge (constant in plasma, def. 2)	2
rhstop	max. value of ρ on exit (def. 0.96)	0.96
xzsrch	vert. pos. for seach of magn. axis (def. 0) [cm]	0

The settings in Table 3.4 represent the launcher settings, and beam settings. Most importantly length-units are in centimeters and angles are in degrees. The following list explains setting choices:

- **xrtol,xatol**: the error tolerances are smaller than set for TORAY ($5 \cdot 10^{-5} > 3 \cdot 10^{-7}$), because this was used in the previous implementation of TORBEAM on TCV and yielded consistent results.
- **xryyb, xrzzb, xwyyb, xwzzb**: the initial principal curvature and width were requested for #58787 using *gdat*. Together they determine the beam waist and curvature as the beam enters the plasma. The setting of TORBEAM are compared to TORAY in Figure 3.2.
- **xordeg, xpoldeg, xxb, xyb, xzb**: the launch parameters ($\text{xordeg}:\text{xzb}$) change for different launcher configurations.

Figure 3.2: The ray pattern and beam waist of TORAY and TORBEAM upon plasma entrance. These were extracted from figures 3.4 and 3.5.

3.3 Testing Environment and Input Conversion

At TCV, TORBEAM is implemented in Matlab Simulink on the LAC server. The source code of TORBEAM is written in the Fortran 90 language and compiled into a Shared Object (SO) file. The SO file is called in by a C MEX S-function in a Simulink library block. The library is integrated in a Simulink model that requires the following inputs.

- **ang_data**: consisting of launcher number, and launching angles (ϕ_L, θ_L) , see also Figure 2.3. These can be requested from TORAY data via Master Data Services (MDS) via *GUIprofs*. The angles are in launcher coordinates and transformed to TORBEAM coordinates with the *ECPOL* toolbox [4] using conventions in Appendix A.
- **prof_data**: consisting of experimental temperature and density profiles in normalized poloidal flux coordinates $(\rho = \sqrt{\psi})$. These can also be requested via MDS or *GUIprofs*.
- **eq_data**: containing the magnetic fields in toroidal (B_ϕ), radial (B_R) and vertical (B_Z) directions. As well as the poloidal magnetic flux ($\psi_{TORBEAM,17}$), the flux on the LCFS (FB) and the vertical position of the magnetic axis (zA corresponding to *xzsrch* in Table 3.4).

The magnetic equilibrium is reconstructed by the LIUQE code [13] from measurement data that is requested via MDS. The reconstructed equilibrium is in tokamak Coordinate Convention (CO-COS) 5 and converted to COCOS 17 for TORBEAM ($\psi_{TORBEAM,17} = -\psi_{LIUQE,5}/\pi$) [20]. The magnetic fields are calculated as $B_R = -\frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{1}{R} \frac{\partial \psi_{TBM,17}}{\partial Z}$ and $B_Z = \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{1}{R} \frac{\partial \psi_{TBM,17}}{\partial R}$ [20], where the partial derivatives are approximated with central differences and edges are retained by backward and forward differences. The influence of the plasma on toroidal magnetic field ($B - \phi$) is determined by LIUQE and reduces the grid size like the central differences. The edge grid points are restored using the $1/R$ dependence of the magnetic field.

3.4 Comparison TORBEAM 2.0 and TORAY-GA

In the following sections, the TORBEAM 2.0 code is compared to the TORAY-GA implementation at TCV. First, real-time TORBEAM is compared to TORAY-GA for single rays and different antenna settings. Then the beam of TORBEAM is compared to 12 rays traced by TORAY-GA from a single antenna to verify the beam geometry and the power and current densities are similar. Similar results are obtained with 50 rays. The current drive scaling with density and temperature is compared to TORAY for the LinLiu routine and differences are inspected for the extended LinLiu+Mom routine. Lastly, full shot performance is compared for two shots where real-time TORBEAM could have been used for control purposes [8], [5].

3.4.1 Ray Geometry of Real-Time TORBEAM 2.0 and TORAY-GA

This section will verify that the same input angles, magnetic equilibrium, and profiles are used by TORAY and TORBEAM. Firstly, to compare the angles, 21 single rays with 21 antennas that represent varying launch settings are traced with real-time TORBEAM and TORAY-GA. This ray comparison is visible in Figure 3.3, the blue ray paths are determined by TORAY and the red lines correspond to the launch angles from TORBEAM. The red lines connect to the blue lines at the LCFS and hence the input angles of the codes are similar. Secondly, to compare the magnetic equilibrium, the flux map was taken from TORAY and converted to the TORBEAM convention. The converted map is visible in the poloidal plane with the LCFS marking the edge of the plasma in bold black. The LCFS touches the heads and tails of the ray paths from TORAY. This verifies the magnetic equilibrium conversion because TORAY determines the ray paths inside the plasma up to the edge. Lastly, the density and temperature profile are based on the toroidal normalized radius ρ_ϕ for TORAY while TORBEAM requires the poloidal normalized radius ρ_ψ .

In addition to the input verification, it can be seen that the locations of maximum absorption, marked as '+', are on top of the magnetic resonant axis for perpendicular injection. However, the crosses move upstream, towards the launcher, as the rays are injected more tangentially in the toroidal plane. In this case, the parallel velocity of the electrons with respect to the injected wave adds a term to the resonance condition (Equation 2.2) and causes a Doppler shift. The parallel Doppler shifted frequency of the wave is smaller and corresponds to a cyclotron frequency in smaller magnetic fields (towards the launcher). The blue line corresponds to a constant cyclotron frequency, without a Doppler shift. Hence the '+' are not on top of the blue line for tangential injection. For perpendicular injection the pointers ('+') are on the resonance (Appendix C.1).

Figure 3.3: Comparison between TORAY in blue and real-time TORBEAM (RT-TBM) in red with a varying poloidal angle θ_L and constant toroidal launching angle ϕ_L for equatorial launcher 4 in #58787. The trajectories of the 21 rays in the plasma are plotted for TORAY, whereas only the set launching directions are plotted for TORBEAM (since it does not return a trajectory). On the right the deposition power and location (see also Figure 4.2) are visible above the temperature and density profiles.

3.4.2 Beam Comparison between TORBEAM 2.0 and TORAY-GA

The comparison in the previous section showed that the inputs of TORAY and TORBEAM are similar and that the rays of TORAY and real-time TORBEAM correspond well. In this section the comparison is extended towards full beams for TORBEAM and TORAY. This beam comparison is visible in Figure 3.4, where a beam is launched into the plasma from upper launcher 6 for temperatures below 2 keV and particle densities below $2 \cdot 10^{19}/m^3$. TORAY is represented by 12 blue rays and TORBEAM (in red) by a central ray and four peripheral rays. The peripheral rays correspond to the $1/e^2$ Gaussian envelope of the beam power over its radius. The central ray of TORAY enters the plasma 0.2 mm lower and leaves 1 mm lower on the Z-axis than the central ray of TORBEAM. The peripheral rays diverge to the order of a centimeter.

Beams also allow the calculation of the power and current densities over the normalized radius ρ . These density distributions can be used to determine the deposition width of the beam and a peak deposition location by means of a Gaussian fit. This can be seen on the right in Figure 3.4, where current and power densities are fitted by Gaussians and the peak deposition location of real-time TORBEAM is the vertical black line. The titles contain the Coefficients of Determination (R^2) for the Gaussian fits [14]. The Coefficient of Determination is the percentage of variance in the data that is explained by the fit.

By definition, TORBEAM has a Gaussian profile and therefore R^2 equals one (for the standard deposition profile [16]). For TORAY the R^2 is above 0.95 and considered a reasonable fit since only twelve rays are used and typically 30-100 are used to approximate a beam [9]. For the power density fits the peak locations differ by $\Delta\rho = 1.5 \cdot 10^{-2}$ [-] and the standard deviations differ by $\Delta\sigma = 1 \cdot 10^{-2}$ [-]. The location and amplitude of the current density are at the same order of magnitude for TORAY and TORBEAM, but can only be compared proportionally because the conversion between different definitions was roughly approximated (see Appendix B).

Figure 3.4: Comparison between TORAY in blue, TORBEAM in red and real-time TORBEAM in black (only the circle) with a toroidal launching angle $\phi_L = -18.8$ degrees for upper launcher 6 in #56701. The trajectories of 12 rays are visible for TORAY, the trajectories of the central and four peripheral rays constitute the beam for TORBEAM, while the real-time version is only present as a black circle in the poloidal plane denoting the point of highest absorption.

In Figure 3.5 the beam comparison is repeated with 50 rays for TORAY, less tense density and temperature profiles and compared to 3.4. The outer rays of TORAY are now outside the peripheral rays of TORBEAM and (since the R^2 values increased from 0.95 to 0.99) the deposition profiles of TORAY have become more Gaussian. The Gaussian profiles of TORAY, however, seem visually smaller for 50 rays than for 12 rays. This is not reflected by the fraction of absorbed power which is 84% for both 12 and 50 rays, but could be explained by a small shift to larger ρ that corresponds to a larger plasma volume in which the beam is deposited. TORBEAM predicts 93% absorption. The ray patterns and waist of the beam as it upon plasma entrance can be seen in Figure 3.2. TORBEAM does have a larger waist at the plasma entrance, but since the absolute power deposition is only evaluated on the central ray [16], this is not likely to cause the difference in power absorption.

Figure 3.5: Comparison between TORAY in blue, TORBEAM in red and real-time TORBEAM in black (only the circle with a toroidal launching angle $\phi_L = -18.8$ degrees for launcher 6 in #56701. As extension to Figure 3.4 TORAY approximates the beam with 50 rays and less tense profiles have been used. The most outer rays are now outside the peripheral rays of TORBEAM. The power density in the top right shows that the distribution is fairly similar, but TORAY deposits less power than TORBEAM. The ray pattern and waist of the beam are visible in Figure 3.2.

3.4.3 Scaling with Temperature and Density

In the previous sections it was shown that the ray and beam launching geometry of TORAY and TORBEAM are similar. This section investigates the dependence on the electron density and temperature for the current drive. The theoretical current drive efficiency is defined in Equation 3.12 [10].

$$\zeta^* \equiv \frac{e^3 n_e \langle j_{\parallel} \rangle}{\varepsilon_0^2 T_e 2\pi Q} \quad (3.12)$$

Where e is the electron charge, ε_0 the vacuum permittivity, Q the power density, and $\langle j_{\parallel} \rangle$ the current density driven by the launcher. It can be seen that the current drive efficiency scales with the electron density n_e and over the electron temperature T_e . This dependence is investigated on #58787 with launchers 4 and 6 for $\rho < 0.2$ (on axis) and $\rho \approx 0.5$ (off axis). The density scaling is investigated using the six density profiles together with the blue temperature profile in Figure 3.6. Similarly, the temperature scaling is investigated using the temperature profiles and the blue density profile in Figure 3.6.

Figure 3.6: Density and temperature profiles used to investigate the current drive and power deposition. The blue density profile is combined with the six temperature profiles and vice versa.

In these investigations both the LinLiu and LinLiu+Mom routines of (real-time) TORBEAM are compared to TORAY. The LinLiu routine is based on the high speed limit approximation and should be similar to TORAY, while the LinLiu+Mom routine considers parallel momentum conservation. In the high speed limit it is assumed that absorption is dominated by suprathermal electrons of which the velocity is much larger than the bulk thermal velocity ($u \gg v_{th}$). Unfortunately, this is not valid in high-temperature plasmas where the energy range of electrons that make the main contribution to ECCD is not so far from the bulk electrons [12]. The LinLiu+Mom routine with parallel momentum conservation in like-particle collisions is expected to be much more precise and to predict 10 to 30 percent larger currents [12]. In case of highly oblique beam propagation in optically thick plasmas the difference between LinLiu and LinLiu+Mom should become small [12].

In the following sections the results obtained with launcher 4 aimed at the magnetic axis and aimed at $\rho = 0.6$ will be shown. Similar results on launcher 6 can be found in Appendix C.3 In all cases the power absorption is presented because the current drive efficiency depends on Q and the deposition location is shown as it determines the temperature and density at deposition in Figure 3.6. It must be noted that the deposition locations are inferred from the Gaussian fits as presented in Figure 3.4 and are not accepted if $R^2 < 0.95$. The density data are not mirrored on the magnetic axis and the Gaussian fit mostly overestimates the peak location of TORAY near the magnetic axis.

On Axis

In Figure 3.7 the scaling of the current drive and power deposition is investigated for an equatorial launcher aimed close to the magnetic axis ($\rho \approx 0.15$). The poloidal cross-section represents the on axis injection of a beam for the blue density and temperature profiles. The toroidal angle $\phi_L = -154^\circ$ corresponds to counter-clockwise toroidal injection (similar to Figure 3.4).

In the bottom, the peak deposition locations of the power are presented versus temperature and density. For increasing temperatures, it can be seen that for TORAY the deposition location decreases ($\rho = 0.2 \rightarrow 0.1$), while TORBEAM remains at a similar level ($\rho \approx 0.17$). For increasing densities, the deposition location first moves towards the magnetic axis (TORAY), but as densities increase the beam is partially reflected and deposition moves towards the launcher.

In the middle, it can be seen that the beam power is absorbed for all temperature profiles and for density profiles below $3 \cdot 10^{19}/m^3$. At higher densities the beam is (partially) reflected and the power absorption drops to the point where no power is absorbed at $5 \cdot 10^{19}/m^3$ (Appendix C.4). The reduction in power absorption starts earlier for TORAY than for TORBEAM.

Finally, the top boxes show the current drive versus the temperature and density. The TORBEAM results with the LinLiu routine show similar scaling as TORAY for the temperature, while the LinLiu+Mom routine scales faster with the temperature and predicts up to 20% more current for the high temperature case. The current scales similarly for all codes and routines for the density, although a little less for TORAY. It was expected that the LinLiu+Mom would predict higher currents because parallel momentum conservation adds the current driven by non-suprathermal electrons. In the current analysis it is noted that the routines all seem to be working and give expected results, but for further readings the reader is referred to [12].

Figure 3.7: The scaling of current drive versus temperature and density for launcher 4 aimed at the magnetic axis. On the left the launching geometry and magnetic equilibrium show the on axis launcher aim for the blue profiles in Figure 3.6. The top two boxes show scaling for TORAY, TORBEAM and real-time TORBEAM to be proportional to density over temperature. The LinLiu+Mom routine predicts up to 20% more current drive than the LinLiu (TORAY setting) routine. The bottom shows that TORAY is able to produce on axis deposition while TORBEAM has difficulties (for $\rho < 0.15$).

Off Axis

In Figure 3.8 the scaling of the current drive and power deposition is investigated for an equatorial launcher aimed at $\rho \approx 0.6$). The poloidal cross-section represents the on axis injection of a beam for the blue density and temperature profiles. The toroidal angle $\phi_L = -154^\circ$ corresponds to counter-clockwise toroidal injection (similar to Figure 3.4).

In the bottom, the peak deposition locations of the power are presented versus temperature and density. For increasing temperatures, it can be seen that for TORAY the deposition location is constant for all codes ($\rho \approx 0.65$). For increasing densities, the deposition location moves towards the launcher and increases from $\rho = 0.6$ to $\rho = 0.7$, again for all codes.

In the middle, it can be seen that the beam power is not absorbed as much by TORAY as it is by TORBEAM for low temperatures and that the same holds for low densities. It is not clear why this occurs. At higher densities and temperatures the absorption of TORAY becomes closer to TORBEAM.

Finally, the top boxes show the current drive versus the temperature and density. The lower power absorption at low densities and temperatures alters the slope of the current drive presented by TORAY. Looking at the higher densities and temperatures, it can be seen that the current scales similarly for all codes and routines for the density and temperature. The LinLiu+Mom routine does not predict higher values because the electron temperature is much lower than on the magnetic axis and thus the high speed limit assumption used in LinLiu holds and mostly suprathermal electrons are involved in the cyclotron interaction. This directly means that the contribution of parallel momentum conservation is negligible [12].

Figure 3.8: The scaling of current drive versus temperature and density for launcher 4 aimed at $\rho \approx 0.5$. On the left the launching geometry and magnetic equilibrium show the off axis launcher aim for the blue profiles in Figure 3.6. The top two boxes show scaling for TORAY, TORBEAM and real-time TORBEAM to be proportional to density over temperature. TORBEAM scales similarly for the LinLiu+Mom routine and the LinLiu routine, while TORAY has a less negative slope resulting in a smaller current drive. The middle shows that more power is absorbed by TORBEAM and that the difference disappears at high densities. The bottom shows that TORAY and TORBEAM deposition locations are very similar off axis. The beam power was 0.4239 MW.

3.4.4 Full shot comparison TORBEAM and TORAY

In the previous sections it has been shown that TORBEAM produces current drive scaling with temperature and density that is similar to TORAY. In this section TORAY, TORBEAM and real-time TORBEAM are used to determine the current, power and deposition location during #58787 and # 56701. These shots were selected because there are multiple neoclassical tearing modes that disturb the plasma equilibrium and because a launcher moved across various deposition locations. TORAY used 12 rays to approximate a beam.

For #58787, Figure 3.9 shows electron temperatures and densities around 2-3 keV and $2 \cdot 10^{19}/m^3$. The deposition location of the peak power density (ρ_P) is similar for all codes and routines. Near the magnetic axis, TORAY reaches near zero deposition while TORBEAM cannot reach surfaces below $\rho = 0.1$. The power deposition of TORBEAM and TORAY is nearly identical during the shot. As such the current drive is also nearly identical. The only difference occurs around $t=1$ second where the higher on-axis electron temperatures cause LinLiu+Mom to predict larger currents [12].

For #56701, Figure 3.9 shows a large range of electron temperatures (2-7 keV) and relative low densities ($n_e < 2 \cdot 10^{19}/m^3$). At the start of the shot the launchers are aimed at the magnetic axis where 99% of the power is absorbed for TORAY and TORBEAM. However, TORAY predicts smaller currents while it was expected to be close to TORBEAM (with the LinLiu routine). This could be an effect of the `nprofcalc` setting (see Appendix C.2). Between $t=1$ and $t=1.2$ seconds less power absorption is predicted by TORAY compared to TORBEAM. In this case, the rays of TORAY deposit between 74% and 93% averaging to 84% while the central ray of TORBEAM deposits 92%. This case was presented in figures 3.5 and 3.4. In the end, TORBEAM with the LinLiu+Mom routine predicts increasingly higher currents for increasing temperatures [12].

Figure 3.9: A comparison between TORAY, TORBEAM and real-time TORBEAM on #58787 with moving launchers, neoclassical tearing modes but relative constant temperature and density profiles and #56701 which adds low densities with high temperatures and shows discrepancies between the codes. The beam power was 0.4239 MW.

3.5 Discussion

The TORBEAM and real-time TORBEAM implementation have both been implemented on TCV and compared to the available TORAY raytracing code. The code settings were matched up to a few small differences such as the error tolerances in the solvers and the solver options as the codes have different implementations of similar approximations. In Figure 3.3, the launch settings of TORAY and real-time TORBEAM are shown to be similar. In Figure 3.4 that resulted in small spatial errors, of less than 1 mm, between the central ray of TORAY and TORBEAM. The spatial errors on the peripheral rays of the beam are larger but still below 1 cm, because of beam diffraction effects and discrepancies in the beam waist and curvature input parameters for TORAY and TORBEAM. The power and current densities of TORAY and TORBEAM are similar, but the current density was only comparable in proportionality. The error on the peak power deposition location ρ was smaller than 0.02 for off axis deposition scenarios and overestimated for on axis due to the analysis with a Gaussian fit on TORAY and the standard deposition profile on TORBEAM for setting `nprofcalc`.

One of the important results of this section is that the power absorption of TORAY seems to reduce earlier than for TORBEAM in low density and off axis cases. This discrepancy is likely caused by the rays of TORAY that experience significantly lower densities and temperatures at the beam periphery. TORBEAM is likely to overestimate absorption in this periphery as it only evaluates the central ray. Still this does not account for the 10% discrepancy in power absorption. The most important result is that TORBEAM and TORAY are predicting similar current drive and power deposition in the moderate density and temperature of #58787 in Figure 3.9 where the difference between LinLiu and LinLiu+momentum are expected to be small [12]. Moreover, the LinLiu routine scales similar to TORAY, while the LinLiu+Mom routine predicts higher currents at higher electron temperatures in Figure 3.7. This corresponds to the predictions in [12]. At high electron temperatures and weakly oblique injection angles the contribution of momentum in the physically more correct LinLiu+Mom routine is relatively large and it is recommended to use TORBEAM with momentum to evaluate the current drive [12]. At locations with high density gradients and low densities it can occur that the peripheral rays have significantly less power absorption. It is noted that in these cases the central ray of TORBEAM predicts slightly higher absorption than the central ray of TORAY ($\approx 1\%$, see Figure 3.3), however, this difference is smaller than the difference with the peripheral rays of TORAY ($\approx 10\%$). Since TORBEAM only considers power absorption on the central ray, it is likely that in these cases the power absorption by TORAY is more correct than the power absorption by TORBEAM.

The current implementation of real-time TORBEAM is thus working and producing results that are consistent with TORAY. This validates implementation of the MEX C S-function in Simulink. The current drive prediction of real-time TORBEAM can be used in the real-time modified Rutherford equation (MRE) to make decisions about the real-time control or mitigation of neoclassical tearing mode [8]. Unfortunately the current density deposition would be a better input for the real-time MRE and the prediction of real-time TORBEAM is based on a ray while the standard deposition profile in TORBEAM is in correspondence with TORAY and assumes the deposition width of individual rays to have little to contribution to the width of the current drive deposition (see also Figure 2.4). Hence, a good real-time estimation of the current and power deposition width should be added to the forward ray tracing scheme.

Chapter 4

Inverse Ray Tracing

Inverse raytracing can be used as part of the actuation in the control process. The user specifies a desired flux surface to deposit heat or drive current and the actuator should aim there. The problem can be classified as the inversion of the C2 continuous function $\rho = f(\theta, \phi, t)$. The determination of an inverse in real-time can be formulated as an optimization problem. This inversion is subject to the following constraints and requirements.

Requirements

- **(Static/Dynamic)** The inversion must cope with a dynamic plasma.
- **(Fast)** The launcher can move with 1° every 10 ms, thus the algorithm should follow plasmas with at least this speed and preferably three to ten times faster. It should also converge the required accuracy within 8 iterations (40 ms)
- **(Accurate)** The maximum error in ρ (after convergence) must not exceed the difference between RT-TORBEAM and TORBEAM. On ASDEX Upgrade this was at most 0.03 [18].
- **(Robust)** The algorithm should cope with unfeasible target locations and failed runs of real-time TORBEAM (there are output flags).

Constraints

- Real-time TORBEAM runs in 5 ms.
- The inversion is constrained to a single core, TORBEAM can not run in parallel.
- The implementation is within the Matlab/Simulink environment.

The following sections will elaborate on the available information in the magnetic equilibrium and how this information is accessed. Then the problem is formalized in terms of a static optimization problem. This is solved for and the results are discussed. Subsequently, the optimization problem is extended towards a dynamic optimization problem. This is not fully solved, but results are discussed and a recommendation is made.

4.1 Available Information

This section will evaluate a straight line inversion based on the reactor and launcher geometry and compare it to the ray-tracing code real-time TORBEAM. The implementation of most algorithms will require some prior knowledge on the map $\rho = h(\theta, \phi, t)$. Prior knowledge is available in the magnetic equilibrium from the equilibrium reconstruction code LIUQE. This equilibrium includes the poloidal flux (ψ) and toroidal magnetic field (B_t) on a grid. Also, the poloidal flux at the separatrix (ψ_s) and the magnetic axis (ψ_a) as well as the position of the magnetic axis (Z_a, R_a) are available. The information about the poloidal flux enables the determination of the flux surface on every grid-point through its definition [18]:

$$\rho = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\psi - \psi_a}{\psi_s - \psi_a}\right)}. \quad (4.1)$$

The dominant toroidal magnetic field determines the Electron Cyclotron (EC) frequency in the plasma. The plasma interacts with the EC waves when the EC frequency or one of its harmonics coincide with the wave frequency. This wave-particle resonance occurs mainly at the second EC harmonic for the X-2 launchers and at the third EC harmonic for the X-3 launchers. Combining the information on the normalized flux and the magnetic resonance, a straight line approximation from the launcher location to the target location can be used to determine the poloidal launching angle θ_{launch} (see Appendix D). The information inside the magnetic equilibrium can be used more accurately with the real-time TORBEAM raytracing code. A map $\rho = h(\theta, \phi, t)$ as determined real-time TORBEAM and by the straight line approximation are visible in Figure 4.1. It can be seen that the straight line inverse is producing results in the shooting domain of real-time TORBEAM. The straight line inverse runs in approximately 4 μs on LAC8 at TCv.

Figure 4.1: Illustration of the straight line approximation.

4.2 Problem Definition

Mathematically, the optimization can be formulated as the minimization of a function subject to constraints on its variables. The inverse raytracing problem can be formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \min_{\theta \in \mathcal{R}^1} f(\theta) &= (\rho_t - h(\theta))^2, \\
 \text{subject to } \theta &\in \mathcal{D} \in (5^\circ, 55^\circ) \cap \mathcal{P}, \\
 \text{with } \mathcal{P} &\in [h^{-1}(\rho_{LCFS}^- - \delta_1), h^{-1}(\rho_{LCFS}^+ - \delta_2)], \\
 \text{and subject to } h(\theta) &\in \mathcal{R}, \\
 \text{where } \mathcal{R} &= (\min_{\theta} h(\theta), \max(\rho_{LCFS}^- - \delta_1, \rho_{LCFS}^+ - \delta_2)],
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.2}$$

where f is the objective function, where $h(\theta)$ originates from the map $\rho = h(\theta)$ and the subscript t replaces *target* to allow shorter notation. The objective function is subject to the constraint that limits the angles θ to be in \mathcal{D} . The domain \mathcal{D} is defined as the intersection between possible launch angles $(5,55)$ and \mathcal{P} , related to the plasma shape and position. The plasma last closed flux surface determines the angles in which the plasma can be targeted. The LCFS itself cannot be a target because there are not enough particles to absorb the beam (there is an output flag for this). To denote that absorption is not possible at the plasma boundary ($\rho = 1$), the inverses ($h^{-1}(\rho)$) are offset by $\delta_{(1,2)}$.

The objective is minimized when the inverse of $h(\theta)$ is determined as $\theta = \theta_t = h^{-1}(\rho_t)$. This is only required in the neighborhood of (ρ_t, θ_t) . Non-unique solutions exist in the range of the mapping bounded by the smallest and largest reachable surfaces ($h(\theta) \in \mathcal{R}$). In order to obtain the inverse h^{-1} it is required to approximate the map $\rho = h(\theta)$ in a model. Local minimizers can be identified by evaluating if the gradient of f is equal to zero and if the Hessian of f is positive definite in the free space. The function $h(\theta)$ can be seen in the right top of Figure 4.2 and is C1 continuous for $\theta \in \tilde{\mathcal{D}} = (5^\circ, 45^\circ]$. Therefore, f is *smooth*, twice differentiable and thus a minimizer can be found via the gradient and Hessian [15].

With the above objective function, the *trust region* strategy is used to search for a minimizer. In this strategy, information gathered about f is used to construct a *model function* m_k with similar behavior near the current guess θ_k . The candidate step p is determined by approximately solving:

$$\min_p m_k(\theta_k + p_k). \tag{4.3}$$

Since the approximation might not be very good the minimizer of m_k is restricted to a region around θ_k in which the model is trusted. This trust region can be modified throughout iterations based on predicted and actual reduction in the objective function [2]. The approach does require information to construct a *model function* and to define a *trust region* in which a solution can be searched. This information is gathered as the algorithm progresses from the initial guess θ_0 and generates a sequence of iterates $\{\theta_k\}_{k=0}^n$ that terminates at the end of a shot.

The iterates of a search algorithm during a shot on a static plasma are visible in Figure 4.2 as red dots. The sequence of the dots is reserved for later sections, for now it is noted that the dots concentrate around surfaces that were targeted during the shot, that is $\rho = 1/2$, $\rho = 2/3$, and $\rho = 0$. For $\rho_t = 2/1$ and $\rho_t = 2/3$ there are solutions for $h^{-1}(\rho_t)$ at the left and right side of the minimum in $h(\theta)$, for this case the algorithm should select the left solution. This algorithm did search on the wrong side of the minimum and guesses were made outside the ideal domain $\tilde{\mathcal{D}} = (5^\circ, 45^\circ]$, at 46° . The domain \mathcal{D} was estimated by the straight line inverse because it depends on the inverse of the map, while the algorithm requires information on the minimum of the map ($\min_{\theta} h(\theta)$). These challenges are addressed in the following sections.

Figure 4.2: The map $h(\theta)$ is presented in blue. The domain $\tilde{\mathcal{D}} = (5^\circ, 55^\circ) \cap [0^\circ, 45^\circ] = (5^\circ, 45^\circ]$ excludes the inconsistent absorption above 45° . At these highly oblique injection angles (see Figure 3.3) real-time TORBEAM occasionally returns $\rho = -1$ with an output Flag $\neq 0$, this causes the jumps and chaos. The red dots denote the iterates of a search algorithm during a shot. The dots concentrate around surfaces that were targeted during the shot, that is $\rho = 1/2$, $\rho = 2/3$, and $\rho = 0$. It is noted that it is undesirable for an algorithm to search a solution to the right of the minimum in $h(\theta)$ and that angles are guessed outside $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}$, at 46° . The region \mathcal{D} should thus have been smaller, but this is not trivial since \mathcal{D} depends on the inverse that is searched. In this case it was roughly approximated by the straight line inverse of Section 4.1 as the minimum location (approximated by 41°) + 5° .

4.3 Static Optimization Routine

In the following section a routine is presented that aims to find the inverse on a single processor while assuming a static plasma as a first investigation. Starting from the objective function in Equation 4.2 and following the approach in [15], the map $h(\theta)$ as visible in the top right of 4.1 is approximated by a straight line model function:

$$\hat{h}(\theta) = a\theta + b. \quad (4.4)$$

By substitution of 4.4 in 4.2 the minimizer of the approximate objective is determined via the derivative ($df/d\theta = 0$):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\hat{f}}{d\theta} &= \frac{d}{d\theta} (\rho_t - \hat{h}(\theta))^2, \\ &= \frac{d}{d\theta} (\rho_t - a\theta - b)^2, \\ &= -2a(\rho_t - a\theta - b), \\ &= (\rho_t - a\theta - b) = 0, \\ \rightarrow \theta^* &= \frac{\rho_t - b}{a} \text{ for } a \neq 0. \end{aligned} \quad (4.5)$$

The second derivative is positive $a^2 > 0$ (for $a \neq 0$) and hence θ^* is a minimizer of the approximation. The model function can be calculated from previous iterates via the variables a and b as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} a_k &= \frac{(\rho_k - \rho_{k-1})}{(\theta_k - \theta_{k-1})}, \\ b_k &= \rho_k - a_k\theta_k, \end{aligned} \quad (4.6)$$

where θ_k is the iterate at iteration k and ρ_k the corresponding deposition location as determined by TORBEAM. Substitution of Equation 4.6 into 4.5 results in the following minimizer θ^* :

$$\theta^* = \frac{\rho_t - b}{a} = \frac{\rho_t - \rho_k + a_k\theta_k}{a_k}, \quad (4.7)$$

where ρ_t denotes the target deposition location. A step from the current iterate θ_k results in the quasi-Newton step p :

$$p_k = \theta^* - \theta_k = \frac{\rho_t - b_k}{a_k} - \theta_k = \frac{\rho_t - \rho_k}{a_k}. \quad (4.8)$$

The next step is taken as $\theta_{k+1} = \theta_k + p_k$ if the full newton step is taken and no trust region is applied. A trust region T can be used to damp the steps if they are too large as follows:

$$p_k = \min(\max(\hat{p}_k, p_{min}), T), \quad (4.9)$$

where the lower bound is $p_{min} > 0$ should be chosen larger than zero such that a step is taken and the slope a is nonzero, this is a filter in which the previous guess is the dominant pair [15]. The trust region T damps the newton step if it is too large. The algorithm requires two points to determine a and b and to startup. The first point is guessed by the straight line inverse and for the second guess the launching angle is changed by one degree.

Results

The algorithm is tested with a relatively large trust region of 5° . The trust region is decreased until the error of the estimate ρ_k is within the error of real-time TORBEAM, which is taken as 0.01 [18] for off axis scenarios and 0.1 for on axis scenarios because of the inability of TORBEAM to produce on axis deposition. A static plasma from #58787 at $t=1.1$ second is used together with launcher 4 for target locations ranging from $\rho_t = 0$ to $\rho = 0.7$. The results in terms of angle θ_k , deposition location ρ_k and absolute error in deposition location $|\rho_t - \rho_k|$ are presented in Figure 4.3. It can be seen that, due to the startup, the first step is relatively far of and the second guess always adds a degree to the angle. After four iterates the algorithm is converged for all targets other than $\rho_t = 0$. The target $\rho_t = 0$ even oscillates and displays undesired behavior. The target location is not reachable and the minimum of the map is approached (see Figure 4.1) which results in $a \approx 0$. That means that the approximation is no longer valid and a trust region should be used to reduce the step size. Reducing the Trust region from 5° to 0.5° the results in much more solid performance in the purple line. For off axis deposition the algorithm converges in about 4 iterates where the first two are part of the startup.

Figure 4.3: Implementation of model based line search on a static plasma for three static target locations $\rho_t = 0, \rho_t = 1/2, \rho_t = 2/3$. In the top the forward traced deposition locations ρ_k are depicted for the angles θ_k (the middle) at iterates k . The red line in the top denotes the minimum reachable location. The bottom depicts the absolute distance to the target location. The red line in the bottom plot denotes the accuracy of real-time TORBEAM. The case in which the algorithm does not converge corresponds to an infeasible target location with large trust region of $T = 5$. Adequate accuracy is achieved within 4 iterates of which the first 2 are part of a startup process.

4.4 Dynamic Optimization Routine

So far, the problem was described as a static optimization with a constant objective function. However, the objective function changes each iteration due to the dynamics of the plasma. The map $\rho = h(\theta)$ should thus be labeled as $\rho = h_k(\theta)$, where k is coupled to a time t_k during an experiment. The target deposition ρ_t is also subject to change and the goal is to minimize the difference throughout the iterations. These dynamic additions allow for the problem to be reformulated for every iteration:

$$\min_{\theta_k \in \mathbb{R}} f_k(\theta_k) = (\rho_{t,k} - h_k(\theta_k))^2 \quad \text{subject to} \quad \begin{cases} \theta \geq 8[^\circ] \\ \theta \leq 55[^\circ] \end{cases}, \quad (4.10)$$

where the target deposition $\rho_{t,k}$, the evaluated function f_k , and its decision variable θ_k are represented on discrete points in time. It is important to note that there are two sources of change. The first is known a priori as the target deposition location $\rho_{t,k}$. The second is the map $h_k(\theta)$ which is subject to changes originating from the plasma and can be categorized by plasma movement and plasma deformation. At last there is noise present in the form of unaccounted plasma behavior. In the following sections the routine from section 4.3 is extended in two ways to cope with these dynamic requirements.

Firstly, the model function is estimated by a complementary filter that copes with failed TORBEAM runs and could be used to update the plasma equilibrium. In order to derive the complementary filter the model is assumed to remain constant over time

$$h_{k+1} = h_k. \quad (4.11)$$

The model is again approximated by a straight line

$$\hat{h}_k(\theta) = a\theta + b, \quad (4.12)$$

for which the measurements $y_{\rho,k}$ and $y_{\rho,k-1}$ are available

$$\begin{aligned} y_{\rho,k} &= \rho_k = h_k(\theta_k) + n_k, \\ y_{\rho,k-1} &= \rho_{k-1} = h_k(\theta_{k-1}) + n_{k-1}, \end{aligned} \quad (4.13)$$

where n_k represents unexplained phenomena, noise. The estimator should minimize the following asymptotic variance

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} E \left[\left(\rho_k - \hat{h}_k(\theta_k) \right)^2 \right]. \quad (4.14)$$

One well known method is the complementary filter in which the estimate is updated based on the measurements [11].

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{h}_{k+1}(\theta_k) &= \hat{h}_k(\theta_k) + \alpha \left(y_{\rho,k} - \hat{h}_k(\theta_k) \right), \\ \frac{d\hat{h}_{k+1}}{d\theta_{k+1}} &= \frac{d\hat{h}_k}{d\theta_k} + \alpha \left(\frac{y_{\rho,k} - y_{\rho,k-1}}{\theta_k - \theta_{k-1}} - \frac{d\hat{h}_k}{d\theta_k} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (4.15)$$

Which results in the following system:

$$\begin{aligned} a_{k+1}\theta_k + b_{k+1} &= a_k\theta_k + b_k + \alpha \left(y_{\rho,k} - a_k\theta_k - b_k \right), \\ a_{k+1} &= a_k + \alpha_a \left(\frac{y_{\rho,k} - y_{\rho,k-1}}{\theta_k - \theta_{k-1}} - a_k \right), \\ b_{k+1} &= (a_k - a_{k+1})\theta_k + b_k + \alpha_b \left(y_{\rho,k} - a_k\theta_k - b_k \right), \end{aligned} \quad (4.16)$$

where b_{k+1} was deduced by substitution. The innovation gains α_a and α_b can be set to zero if the TORBEAM run was unsuccessful (i.e. Flag $\neq 0$). The step \hat{p}_{k+1} is similar to Equation 4.8.

Secondly, the trust region is adapted based on the straight line inverse and/or the standard adaptive trust region formalism [15]. In the static optimization it was found that the magnetic axis requires a smaller trust region, around 0.5 [°], to reduce the oscillations due to the simple model approximation. The trust region can be dynamic by evaluating the predicted and actual reduction in the objective [15]. The trust region T then depends on the values of objective function evaluations f and the predicted value F :

$$\begin{aligned} f_k &= (\rho_{t,k} - y_{\rho,k})^2, \\ f_{k-1} &= (\rho_{t,k} - y_{\rho,k-1})^2, \\ F_k &= (\rho_{t,k} - \hat{h}_k \theta_k)^2, \\ &= (\rho_{t,k} - a_k \theta_k - b_k)^2. \end{aligned} \quad (4.17)$$

The division between the predicted and actual reduction $\Delta f / \Delta F = \left| \frac{f_k - f_{k-1}}{F_k - f_{k-1}} \right|$ can now be used to evolve the trust region.

$$T_{k+1} = \begin{cases} T_k / (1 + \phi) & \text{if } \Delta f / \Delta F < \epsilon_{Damp} \cap Flag = 0 \\ T_k \cdot (1 + \phi) & \text{if } \Delta f / \Delta F > \epsilon_{Relax} \cap Flag = 0 \\ T_k / (1 + \phi) & \text{if } Flag \neq 0 \\ T_k & \text{elsewhere,} \end{cases} \quad (4.18)$$

where the *Flag* is part of the output of TORBEAM (failed if $Flag \neq 0$). The two important parameters are the criterion for additional damping ϵ_{Damp} and relaxation ϵ_{Relax} . Typically these are set at $\epsilon_{Damp} = 1/4$ and $\epsilon_{Relax} = 3/4$, which means that the predicted reduction is larger than the actual reduction [15]. In this report the golden ratio $\phi = 1.64$ is used to multiply and divide the region. The trust region is bounded by a maximum p_{max} and minimum step length p_{min} as it constrains the model predicted step \hat{p}_k :

$$\begin{aligned} T_{k+1} &= \min(\max(T_k, p_{min}), p_{max}), \\ \hat{p}_{k+1} &= \min(\max(\hat{p}_k, p_{min}), T_{k+1}). \end{aligned} \quad (4.19)$$

It was noted that the algorithm can start shooting at the wrong side of the plasma when the target location changes from on-axis to off-axis ($\rho_t = 0 \rightarrow \rho_t = 0.5$). The constrain $\theta \in \mathcal{D}$ is constantly violated because the objective function can not reach $\rho = 0.5$. The linear model (Eq. 4.12) poorly approximates the magnetic axis, however, the following efforts were made to retain the associated convex objective function. Exclusively reducing the constraint violation, the *feasibility restoration phase* [15] uses the straight line inverse to compute a step to the *feasible* direction (left in Figure 4.2). This requirement is an artifact of the linear approximation the step and trust region can enter a as the target location switches between feasible and unfeasible positions:

$$T_{k+1} = \begin{cases} T_k \cdot (1 + \phi) & \rho_{min} \geq \rho_{t,k} \cap \rho_{min} < \rho_{t,k-1} \\ T_k / (1 + \phi) & \rho_{min} < \rho_{t,k} \cap \rho_{min} \geq \rho_{t,k-1} \\ T_k & \text{elsewhere,} \end{cases} \quad (4.20)$$

$$p_{k+1} = \begin{cases} (p_k + \theta_{SLI})/2 & \text{if } \rho_{min} \geq \rho_{t,k} \cap \rho_{min} < \rho_{t,k-1} \\ (p_k + \theta_{SLI})/2 & \text{if } \rho_{min} < \rho_{t,k} \cap \rho_{min} \geq \rho_{t,k-1} \\ \hat{p}_{k+1} & \text{elsewhere.} \end{cases} \quad (4.21)$$

The straight line inverse can differentiate between locations on the magnetic resonance that are feasible and infeasible. In these two cases the damping and relaxing behavior is different because the model is more trustworthy for $\rho_t > \rho_{min}$. It also serves as a basic extension of the static trust region T_k in Equation 4.9.

$$(\epsilon_{Damp}, \epsilon_{Relax}) = \begin{cases} (\epsilon_{D1}, \epsilon_{R1}) & \text{if } \rho_{min} \geq \rho_{t,k} \\ (\epsilon_{D0}, \epsilon_{R0}) & \text{if } \rho_{min} < \rho_{t,k} \end{cases}, \quad T_{k+1} = \begin{cases} p_{min} & \text{if } \rho_{min} \geq \rho_{t,k} \\ p_{max} & \text{if } \rho_{min} < \rho_{t,k} \end{cases}. \quad (4.22)$$

Table 4.1: Variations of the dynamic optimization algorithm

Version	p_{min} [°]	p_{max} [°]	$(\epsilon_{D0}, \epsilon_{R0})$	$(\epsilon_{D1}, \epsilon_{R1})$	restoration
V1	0.5	5	-	-	no
V2	0.2	5	$(\frac{1}{6}, \frac{5}{4})$	$(\frac{5}{4}, 1)$	no
V3	0.5	5	-	-	yes
V4	0.2	5	$(\frac{1}{6}, \frac{5}{4})$	$(\frac{5}{4}, 1)$	yes

Results

In this section four different versions of the dynamic algorithm are tested with launcher 6. The versions are listed in Table 4.1 where the first version uses the trust region based on the straight line inverse (Eq. 4.22) without a *feasibility restoration phase*. The second version uses the adaptive trust region (Eq. 4.18). The third and fourth version are the same but have a *restoration phase*. The routines are tested with a reference that starts at $\rho = 1/2$ goes to the magnetic axis $\rho = 0$ and then towards $\rho = 2/3$. The results can be seen in Figure 4.4. In red the minimum reachable surface ($\rho_{min,reach}$) and accuracy of real-time TORBEAM $\rho_{acc,RT-TBM}$ are presented. The first ten iterations the routines present similar deposition locations with a trust region $T = 5$ and an absolute error below the accuracy of real-time TORBEAM within less than five iterations (that include the startup). At iterate k=11, on-axis deposition is requested and the trust regions of V1 and V3 are set to 0.5° (result in Figure 4.3). This small trust region causing unacceptably small step sizes in θ_k for V1 and V3 from iterate k=10 to k=20. It is recommended to use V4, but with p_{min} set to 2° to be more than three times as fast as the launcher, paying with oscillations.

Figure 4.4: Comparison of line search algorithms (see Table 4.1) to trace the angle θ_k on a static plasma for a dynamic target location (black dashed line in the top plot). The first plot shows the forward traced deposition locations ρ_k as a function of the guessed angles θ_k (second plot) at iterates k . The third plot depicts the trust region T_k at iterates k and the fourth and bottom plot denotes the absolute error of the forward traced and target location in the top plot.

4.5 Discussion

In this chapter the inverse raytracing problem was approached from an optimization perspective. It has been shown that the information of the magnetic equilibrium can be used in a straight line inversion to obtain an approximate launching angle in $4 \mu\text{s}$. However, in Figure 4.1 it can be seen that two large discrepancies are present. Firstly, the straight line inverse does not take into account the dependence of the launch position on the launching angle (θ_L). Secondly, the resonant location inferred from the magnetic equilibrium does not take into account the Doppler shift for oblique injection in the toroidal plane. Similar to the launch location, the toroidal injection angle changes with the launching angle (θ_L).

The straight line inverse is used to startup any optimization routine. In the static optimization routine a linear model function of the map $h(\theta)$ (see Figure 4.2) was used in combination with a static trust region to optimize for three static references ($\rho_t = 0, 1/2, 2/3$). For off-axis, the reference was reached with an accuracy exceeding that of real-time TORBEAM. For on-axis the reference was unfeasible and this resulted in oscillations. The oscillations were reduced by adapting the trust region from 5° to 0.5° . This indicates that the model function is a bad approximation at the magnetic axis, which is in agreement with Figure 4.2, where the linear model function is fitted on a locally quadratic function (at $\theta = 42^\circ$).

The resulting trust regions from the static optimization were used as upper and lower bound on the trust region in the dynamic optimization routine. In the dynamic routine the model function is estimated by a complementary filter that does not update the model function if the real-time TORBEAM run failed ($\text{flag} \neq 0$), which is working well. In addition, the trust region is decreased if the prediction by the model function differs too much from the observed error (via TORBEAM). The trust region can increase if the prediction and actual observation are similar. At last a *feasibility restoration phase* was added to motivate the algorithm to search solutions on the "nice" side of the minimum in Figure 4.2. Settings were tuned and performance was decent for the most advanced routine on a changing reference but with a static plasma.

On a dynamic plasma the algorithm should be able to follow the reference with at least the maximum velocity of the launcher. The Launcher can move with 1° degree every 10 ms. On axis, an accurate non-oscillating solution requires the trust region to decrease to 0.5° degree. TORBEAM should be able to run in 5 ms and thus be able to step 1° degree every 10 ms. This equals the launcher velocity, but presents little margin to enter the undesirable situation where the software-tracing algorithm is slower than the launcher. Off axis the algorithm is accurate with steps up to 5° and thus the current versions are heavily constrained by the linear approximation at the quadratic magnetic axis.

Chapter 5

Conclusion

In conclusion, the new version of (real-time) TORBEAM 2.0 is implemented at TCV. It was found that the power absorption can be overestimated by TORBEAM in cases with low density but high density gradients where some peripheral rays in TORAY show significantly less absorption than the central ray of TORBEAM. It is also verified that the current drive routine that includes parallel momentum conservation (LinLiu+Mom) predicts higher currents than the current drive routine that is based on the high speed limit approximation (LinLiu). The difference is more pronounced at high electron temperatures and weakly oblique injection angles, as predicted by [12]. Moreover, the real-time version of TORBEAM follows the full version closely during a full shot with changing launching angles and inputs. Similarly, the current drive prediction of real-time TORBEAM scales almost identically to TORBEAM for the electron temperature and density.

The new version of TORBEAM is used in a reverse ray-tracing algorithm that aims to find the right launching angle to arrive at a certain deposition location. The problem was approached in two stages. In the first stage, a static plasma, static reference and static trust region routine were used with a linear model function. The trust region had to be decreased near the magnetic axis because the model function is inaccurate in that region. In the second stage, a static plasma, but dynamic reference and dynamic routine were used with a complementary filter to update the linear model function. A *feasibility restoration phase* was added to push the routine to the preferred solution (there can be two solution). It was found that the dynamic trust region algorithm with *restoration phase* converged within four iterations to a changing reference. However, it was also noted that the reduction in the trust region to about 0.5° limits the speed to follow the magnetic axis in a dynamic plasma to about 1° per 10 ms, which is also the speed of the launcher. In order not too constrain the closed loop of the launcher it should be three to ten times faster than the launcher.

In future work, it is required to extend the forward real-time ray-tracing formalism and find a way to estimate the deposition width of the current density in real-time. The real-time modified Rutherford equation requires the driven current and a width of the deposition profile to determine a coefficient. The ray-based estimation of the deposition width from real-time TORBEAM is, however, expected to have little to no influence on the actual deposition width because this is assumed by standard deposition profile routine on TORBEAM .

Other recommendations include testing the dynamic estimation routine from section 4.4 for a dynamic plasma and implementing it in Simulink (if performance is adequate). For faster tracking of the launching angle near the magnetic axis the minimum trust region can be increased at the cost of oscillations. However, it is recommended to increase the complexity of the model by providing a constant positive Hessian with a small magnitude (i.e. 10^{-2}) or by a real-time estimate of the Hessian (i.e. with a complementary-like filter).

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Appendix A

Angle Conventions

Many different coordinate frames can be used to describe the injection angle in spherical coordinates. This appendix aims to mathematically describe them such that there is no discussion about their definition. TORBEAM first rotates around the z_0 axis with an angle ϕ and then rotates θ around y_1 and finally multiplies with a negative identity $-I$ to arrive at the beam frame $\{l_{\parallel}, l_{\perp}^y, l_{\perp}^z\}$.

$$\begin{pmatrix} \ell_{\parallel} \\ \ell_{\perp}^1 \\ \ell_{\perp}^2 \end{pmatrix} = -I \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\theta_{\text{TBM}}) & 0 & \sin(\theta_{\text{TBM}}) \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin(\theta_{\text{TBM}}) & 0 & \cos(\theta_{\text{TBM}}) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\phi_{\text{TBM}}) & \sin(\phi_{\text{TBM}}) & 0 \\ -\sin(\phi_{\text{TBM}}) & \cos(\phi_{\text{TBM}}) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} \ell_{\parallel} \\ \ell_{\perp}^1 \\ \ell_{\perp}^2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -\cos(\phi_{\text{TBM}}) \cos(\theta_{\text{TBM}}) & -\cos(\theta_{\text{TBM}}) \sin(\phi_{\text{TBM}}) & -\sin(\theta_{\text{TBM}}) \\ \sin(\phi_{\text{TBM}}) & -\cos(\phi_{\text{TBM}}) & 0 \\ \cos(\phi_{\text{TBM}}) \sin(\theta_{\text{TBM}}) & \sin(\phi_{\text{TBM}}) \sin(\theta_{\text{TBM}}) & -\cos(\theta_{\text{TBM}}) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

TORAY has almost the same convention but seems to use a strange rotation around θ (disclaimer only l_{\parallel} verified):

$$\begin{pmatrix} \ell_{\parallel} \\ \ell_{\perp}^1 \\ \ell_{\perp}^2 \end{pmatrix} = -I \begin{pmatrix} \sin(\theta_{\text{TOR}}) & 0 & \cos(\theta_{\text{TOR}}) \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\cos(\theta_{\text{TOR}}) & 0 & \sin(\theta_{\text{TOR}}) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\phi_{\text{TOR}}) & \sin(\phi_{\text{TOR}}) & 0 \\ -\sin(\phi_{\text{TOR}}) & \cos(\phi_{\text{TOR}}) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} \ell_{\parallel} \\ \ell_{\perp}^1 \\ \ell_{\perp}^2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -\cos(\phi_{\text{TOR}}) \sin(\theta_{\text{TOR}}) & -\sin(\phi_{\text{TOR}}) \sin(\theta_{\text{TOR}}) & -\cos(\theta_{\text{TOR}}) \\ \sin(\phi_{\text{TOR}}) & -\cos(\phi_{\text{TOR}}) & 0 \\ \cos(\phi_{\text{TOR}}) \cos(\theta_{\text{TOR}}) & \cos(\theta_{\text{TOR}}) \sin(\phi_{\text{TOR}}) & -\sin(\theta_{\text{TOR}}) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

The LAUNCH angles have a convention that guarantees a positive poloidal shooting angle, corresponding with the angle of the launcher as it is implemented physically. The launcher can rotate around the x axis and the mirror itself can rotate around the rotated y axis as follows:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \ell_{\parallel} \\ \ell_{\perp}^1 \\ \ell_{\perp}^2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\theta_{\text{LAU}}) & 0 & \sin(\theta_{\text{LAU}}) \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin(\theta_{\text{LAU}}) & 0 & \cos(\theta_{\text{LAU}}) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos(\phi_{\text{LAU}}) & -\sin(\phi_{\text{LAU}}) \\ 0 & \sin(\phi_{\text{LAU}}) & \cos(\phi_{\text{LAU}}) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} \ell_{\parallel} \\ \ell_{\perp}^1 \\ \ell_{\perp}^2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\theta_{\text{LAU}}) & \sin(\phi_{\text{LAU}}) \sin(\theta_{\text{LAU}}) & \cos(\phi_{\text{LAU}}) \sin(\theta_{\text{LAU}}) \\ 0 & \cos(\phi_{\text{LAU}}) & -\sin(\phi_{\text{LAU}}) \\ -\sin(\theta_{\text{LAU}}) & \cos(\theta_{\text{LAU}}) \sin(\phi_{\text{LAU}}) & \cos(\phi_{\text{LAU}}) \cos(\theta_{\text{LAU}}) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

Appendix B

Current Drive Density

Details about current drive definitions can be found in the notes by O. Sauter [19] or the publication of LinLiu [10]. Following their conventions, the toroidal current density is defined as:

$$\tilde{j}_\phi = dI_\phi/dA_\phi = \frac{\langle j_\phi/R \rangle}{\langle 1/R \rangle} \quad (\text{B.1})$$

Equally important is the current drive using flux function $\gamma(\psi)$ [10] notation:

$$j_{cd} = \frac{\langle j_{cd} \rangle}{\langle B \rangle} B = \gamma(\psi) B \quad (\text{B.2})$$

TORAY uses the following definition [19]:

$$j_{TORAY} = \frac{dI_\phi}{dV} = \frac{\langle j_\phi/R \rangle}{2\pi} = \frac{\tilde{j}_\phi \langle 1/R \rangle}{2\pi} = \frac{\langle j_{cd} \rangle \langle B_\phi/R \rangle \langle 1/R \rangle}{\langle B \rangle \langle 1/R \rangle 2\pi} [A/m^3] \quad (\text{B.3})$$

While TORBEAM uses [10] [16]:

$$j_{TORBEAM} = \langle j_\parallel \rangle = \frac{j_\parallel}{B} \langle B \rangle = -e \left\langle \int d^3v \chi S_{rf}(f_M) \right\rangle \langle B \rangle = \gamma(\psi) \langle B \rangle = \frac{\langle j_{cd} \rangle}{\langle B \rangle} \langle B \rangle [A/m^2] \quad (\text{B.4})$$

Combining the two it is possible to compare TORAY current densities accurately with TORBEAM current densities:

$$j_{TORAY} = j_{TORBEAM} \frac{\langle B_\phi/R \rangle \langle 1/R \rangle}{\langle B \rangle \langle 1/R \rangle 2\pi} [A/m^3] \quad (\text{B.5})$$

Which is proportionally approximated by:

$$j_{TORAY} \cdot 2\pi R_0 \propto j_{TORBEAM} \quad (\text{B.6})$$

It must be noted that the current density conversions as used in this report are only proportional as in the above equation.

Appendix C

Cases of TORAY vs TORBEAM

This appendix contains case comparisons between TORAY and TORBEAM

C.1 Ray Comparison without Doppler Shift

In figures C.1 it can be seen that for perpendicular injection the maximum absorption points are on top of the (not Doppler shifted) magnetic resonance for both equatorial launcher 4 and upper launcher 6.

Figure C.1: Comparison between TORAY in blue and real-time TORBEAM (RT-TBM) in red with a varying poloidal angle θ_L and constant toroidal launching angle ϕ_L for equatorial launcher 4 in #58787 . The trajectories of the 21 rays in the plasma are plotted for TORAY, whereas only the set launching directions are plotted for TORBEAM. In the toroidal plane the rays are injected perpendicular to the plasma.

C.2 On Axis Beam Comparison

In Figure C.2 the current drive discrepant time slice ($t = 0.9$ s) of launcher 6 in #56701 is depicted (see Figure 3.9). It can be seen that the power and current density distributions of TORAY have their peak at $\rho = 0$, complying with the on-axis aim of the launcher. The density profiles of TORBEAM do not comply with the on-axis scenario because the standard deposition profile was used for nprofcalc.

Figure C.2: Comparison between TORAY in blue, TORBEAM in red and real-time TORBEAM in black (only the circle with a toroidal launching angle $\phi_L = -18.6$ degrees for launcher 6 in #56701. TORAY approximates the beam with 50 rays. The most outer rays are outside the peripheral rays of TORBEAM. The power density in the top right shows that the distribution of TORBEAM is not on-axis like TORAY, this is an artifact of the standard deposition profile. TORBEAM uses the LinLiu current drive routine.

C.3 Current Drive Scaling for Launcher Six

In Figure C.3 it can be seen that the current drive on upper launcher 6 scales similar to launcher 4 in Section 3.4.3.

Figure C.3: Illustration of current drive scaling with temperature and density for launcher 6 using the profiles in Figure 3.6.

C.4 Reflectometry

The cases in which the beam is heavily deflected or even reflected in the scaling analysis are depicted below (see also Section 3.4.3 and Appendix C.3).

Figure C.4: Cases of launcher 4 and 6 where the beam is heavily deflected or even reflected.

Appendix D

Straight Line Inverse

The electron cyclotron resonance $f_{EC,n}$ for the n^{th} harmonic can be approximated and compared to the wave frequency f_w as follows

$$f_{EC,n} = \frac{B_t \cdot e \cdot n}{2\pi m_e} = f_w, \quad (\text{D.1})$$

where e is the electron charge and m_e is the electron mass. Solving for the equality of the injected wave frequency and launcher specific harmonic presents a vertical line of grid positions with resonant toroidal magnetic field strengths .

Combining the information on the normalized flux and the magnetic resonance, a straight line approximation from the launcher location to the target location can be used to determine the poloidal launching angle θ_{launch} :

$$\theta_p = \arctan \left(\frac{z_{launch} - z_{target}}{R_{launch} - R_{target}} \right), \quad (\text{D.2})$$

where z and R denote the vertical coordinate and major radius with subscripts for the launcher location *launch* and target deposition location *target*.

The previous approximation is only valid when the sine of the toroidal launching angle $\sin(\phi_L)$ is zero. In the extension to 3D the desired deposition location is constructed by a circle going around the torus as

$$C = C0 + V \cos \zeta + W \sin \zeta = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ z_{target} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} R_{target} \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \cos \zeta + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ R_{target} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \sin \zeta, \quad (\text{D.3})$$

where the angle $\zeta = 0$ determines the position on the circle and is unknown. The plane in which the launcher injects waves can be described in the launching coordinate system by:

$$P_i = P0_i + \vec{v}\xi + \vec{w}\eta = \begin{bmatrix} \xi_{launch} \\ \eta_{launch} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \xi + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \eta, \quad (\text{D.4})$$

where the vectors \vec{v} and \vec{w} and the launching position $P0$ contain the important information whereas the exact values of ξ and η are not important. The subscript i denotes the injection reference coordinate system. The desired launching angle can be inferred via the intersection between the circle and the plane by solving:

$$(C - P) \cdot N = 0, \quad (\text{D.5})$$

where N is $\vec{v} \times \vec{w}$ and thus normal to the plane. The plane first needs to be rotated to be in the same coordinate system representation as:

$$P_l = P0_l + R_\phi (\vec{v}\xi + \vec{w}\eta) = \begin{bmatrix} x_{launch} \\ y_{launch} \\ z_{launch} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} x + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \cos \phi \\ \sin \phi \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{D.6})$$

where the l denotes the launcher coordinates and corresponds to the vacuum vessel with the x axis aligned with the launcher. The conventions on angles and coordinate systems can be found in Equation A.5[4]. Working out the intersection results in the following

$$\left(\begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ z_{target} \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} x_{launch} \\ y_{launch} \\ z_{launch} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} R_{target} \cos \zeta \\ R_{target} \sin \zeta \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ \sin \phi \\ \cos \phi \end{bmatrix} \right) \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ -\cos \phi \\ \sin \phi \end{bmatrix} = 0, \quad (\text{D.7})$$

The orthogonal function products vanish presenting the following solution for the angle ζ in the target circle C .

$$\zeta = \arcsin \left([(z_{target} - z_{launch})(\sin \phi / \cos \phi) + y_{launch}] / R_{target} \right) \quad (\text{D.8})$$

The calculation of $x_{target} = \cos \zeta$ and $y_{target} = \sin \zeta$ allow direct computation of the launching angle.

$$\theta_L = \arctan \left(\sqrt{(y_{target} - y_{launch})^2 + (z_{target} - z_{launch})^2}, |x_{target} - x_{launch}| \right) \cdot \text{sgn}(z_{target} - z_{launch}) \quad (\text{D.9})$$

Note that this straight line approximation is incomplete in three ways. Firstly, the launch position depends on the launching angle as the mirror rotates around a different point than the launching point. Secondly the resonant surface depends on the Doppler shift for oblique injection and this also depends on the launching angle. Thirdly, wave diffraction is not taken into account.